

Letter to the Editor

Gastrointestinal motility in m.3243A>G carriers depends not only on autonomic innervation, but also on several other influencing factors

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The interesting article by Nielsen et al raises some concerns [1].

Firstly, gastrointestinal motility is not only due to autonomic denervation, but also to various other influencing factors. These include the duration of gastrointestinal symptoms, dietary habits, food composition, state of the microbiome, gender, level of physical activity and varying tolerance of the test food. These influencing factors should be included in the analysis to avoid false positive/negative results.

Secondly, neuropathy was only assessed clinically and not by nerve conduction studies (NCS). Since neuropathy may be subclinical and only detectable by NCS testing, neuropathy may have been missed in some patients. It should also be considered that diabetic neuropathy does not always begin as a large fiber neuropathy, but rather as a small fiber neuropathy in which the NCS are normal. Therefore, all patients with normal NCS should have been tested for small fiber neuropathy.

Thirdly, there is a discrepancy between the number of patients with diabetes (n=11), the average duration of diabetes (12 years) and the number of patients with neuropathy (n=8) [1]. With such a long duration of disease, one would expect a higher prevalence of neuropathy. What were the HbA1c levels and duration of diabetes in the three patients with diabetes but without neuropathy? There is also a discrepancy between the low mean HbA1c level and the number of patients with neuropathy [1]. Since the mean HbA1c was low, one would not expect eight patients to have neuropathy. Was there evidence of causes of neuropathy other than diabetes in these 8 patients?

Fourth, the mean heteroplasmy rate was low (25), suggesting that the patients were either asymptomatic or minimally symptomatic [1]. As heteroplasmy rate is one of the determinants of phenotype, one would expect higher heteroplasmy rates in the study cohort as all had at least gastrointestinal dysmotility (GID). One argument for minimal disease expression is the low mean serum lactate. How many of the patients had lactic acidosis?

Fifth, autonomic nervous system involvement was assessed only by calculating cardiac variability [1]. Because autonomic neuropathy may be present without cardiac autonomic dysfunction, some patients with autonomic neuropathy may have been missed. Did any of the 22 patients show clinical manifestations of autonomic neuropathy other than GID?

Finally, discontinuation of laxatives 3d before the test may lead to GID and false positive results on the SmartPill examination. The latency period between discontinuation of laxatives and testing should be longer.

Declarations

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References

- [1] S. R. Nielsen, M. P. Stoico, D. Liao, A. M. Drewes, I. S. Pedersen, A. L. Frederiksen, and C. Brock. Prolonged gastrointestinal transit times and dysmotility in m. 3243A;G Mitochondrial Disease. *Neurogastroenterol Motil.*, e70092, June 2025. doi:10.1111/nmo.70092.